

IMPACT OF COVID 19 ON HIGHER EDUCATION

P KALYANI SREEDEVI, KR ESWAR REDDY, B RAJA SEKHAR REDDY
ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ^{1,2,3}

sreeluraj27@gmail.com, kollagieswar1981@gmail.com, brajasekhar.reddy@gmail.com

Department of English, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,
N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rapthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

ABSTRACT

As the number of confirmed cases and fatalities kept rising, the world became engulfed in the coronavirus pandemic. The effects of COVID-19 have been felt across all industries. Dangerous and life-threatening diseases are spreading rapidly in almost every state in India. The Indian government has closed all schools as one of many precautions to stop the spread of the sickness and its accompanying blackout. This has a devastating effect on India's educational system. Close to 32 crore students cancelled their attendance in K-12, community college, and university. In spite of all that has happened, HEIs have responded constructively and kept the wheels of education turning, keeping research and instruction running with the help of certain resources and methods even as the epidemic has progressed. The lockdown, on the other hand, has generated a number of problems, such as the loss of normal lecturers, the delay of exams and regular lectures, etc., which has reduced the amount of time available for the next school year. Covid-19 has had both beneficial and bad effects on education, and this article discusses the former and offers solutions while focusing on the latter's effects on HEIs.

KeyWords: Covid – 19, higher education, teaching techniques, positive and negative impactsIndia,

INTRODUCTION:

The recently discovered Corona Virus causes the infectious sickness known as coronavirus disease. The first verified fatality occurred in Wuhan on January 9, 2020, and the World Health Organisation (WHO) proclaimed the epidemic a pandemic on March 11, 2020. The outbreak was first discovered in Wuhan, Hubei, China, in December 2019. As shown by the World Health Organisation (WHO), nations must move swiftly and increase their reactions to treat, identify, and decrease transmission in order to save lives. Over 750,000 cases of COVID-19 have been reported in 200 countries and territories as of March 2020, with an estimated 45,000 fatalities and over 1,00,000 recoveries.

A number of preventative steps to lessen the influx and dissemination of the Corona Virus into India have been declared by the government. Maharashtra, Delhi, Kerala, Rajasthan, and Uttar Pradesh have the highest numbers of suspected cases, although the illness has affected several states in India despite efforts by the federal and state governments. As a first line of defence, the World Health Organisation (WHO) has recommended continuing to isolate oneself from others in light of the current coronavirus pandemic scenario. In order to quarantine the infected individuals, every nation instituted a lockdown. Given the prevailing scenario throughout India, it was absolutely necessary for the state governments to shut down institutions and colleges. Preventative actions against COVID-19 have been initiated by the Indian government. In March and April, the majority of Indian institutions wrap up their academic year. By this point, many colleges and universities have finished teaching all of the required courses and are focusing on final test preparation. The educational institutions were shuttered as a result of choices made by our governments. Exam dates were either postponed or cancelled by educational institutions throughout India. Many schools had to move to online learning during the lockdown since they were unable to hold in-person courses, exams, internships, etc. Educators and students alike were first confused about how to respond to the unexpected crisis that forced the suspension of classes. In the end, however, everyone saw how much the lockdown had taught them. As a result, COVID-19 has presented both obstacles and possibilities for educational institutions to enhance their technical capacities. With the use of digital teaching techniques, both students and instructors were able to keep up with their education. Online assignments and live video lectures were both used by the instructors.

holding meetings with the use of various applications such as Google Meet, Skype, Zoom, Jio Meet, and so on. Teachers established Whatsapp groups consisting of themselves, students, and parents or guardians as a means of communicating with the pupils. Teachers used to have effective communication via e-medium, staying in constant contact to discuss students' academic struggles.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Both the good and bad effects of COVID-19 on education will be highlighted, as will the several steps made by the Indian government to support the education sector throughout the pandemic.

- Chart the course of higher education after COVID-19.

METHODOLOGY

Reports, government websites, newspapers, and E-news were the sources used to compile the data and material for this research. The effect of the COVID-19 epidemic on classroom instruction has been the subject of many scholarly articles and online databases.

Initiatives of Govt. of India on education during Pandemic:

There have been a lot of precautions taken by the Indian government to stop the epidemic in its tracks. All schools throughout the nation were ordered to remain closed on March 16, 2020, by the union administration. All secondary and upper secondary school exams in India were postponed on March 18, 2020, by the Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE). While the Indian government has been implementing new measures to combat the epidemic and periodically extending lockdown periods, schools have remained shuttered nonstop. The government mandated that all schools move their programmes online. The use of digital technologies has been expedited due to the shutdown. The greatest course of action in light of the current COVID-19 epidemic is to pursue education online. The federal government of India, individual state governments, and private entities have all responded appropriately to the epidemic and the subsequent closure of educational institutions. The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has set up a number of things, such as student-oriented web portals and educational television and radio programmes. Students used widely utilised digital applications such as Zoom, Google Meet, YouTube, Jio Meet, etc., while the school was under lockdown. a few of the MHRD's digital projects aimed at universities are detailed here.

E – patashala :

Class 1–12 in many languages is covered via the E-Patashala software developed by NCERT. Teachers and students alike may benefit from the app's E-text and video instruction features. (Subject Matter Experts) are responsible for the creation of the material in this app. Visit either <http://epathshala.nic> or <http://epathshala.gov.in> from your computer.

Diksha

The Diksha portal is an app that students may use to access e-learning materials such as video classes, workbooks, textbooks, and tests. Expert professors have crafted the curriculum with the support of CBSE and NCERT. Textbooks sometimes include QR codes that, when scanned, reveal the contents. Visit <https://diksha.gov.in> or <https://seshaqun.gov.in> on the web to access the Google Play store, where you may download the app.

National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER)

Books, interactive modules, and videos are just a few of the many materials available to instructors and students via this platform, which also offers resources in Hindi and Urdu. Classes 1–12 have

their content linked to their respective curricula. Including materials that are well suited for use in the classroom. At <https://nroer.gov.in/welcome>, you may find the webpage.

Impact of Covid 19 on Education:

Not just in India, but around the world, the whole educational system has been profoundly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. A new strategy had to be implemented or measures had to be taken to mitigate the pandemic's effects to a minimum. The impact was so great that it altered the course of education rather than passing it on. The results, both good and bad. The vast majority of students—about 94% of the world's total—were affected by this epidemic because school systems were forced to close. Consequently, we shall get insight on these effects in the paragraph that follows.

POSITIVE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON EDUCATION:

Concerning COVID-19, inquiries are welcome. Are there any good things that may come out of such a significant catastrophe, a pandemic? The solution is obvious, but the full ramifications won't be known until much later. But looking at the here and now, it's easy to see how some of the areas affected by COVID-19 may be rethought or improved. The use of technology into the educational system is one aspect that comes to mind when thinking about the beneficial effects of pandemic. Technology and education have always worked hand in hand, but the pandemic pushed their relationship to a to new level. Even though this is a forced transition, it was the only fusible option available at the time. The use of modern technology in the classroom does not, however, guarantee that students and teachers will have a more meaningful relationship, where the former will have an easier time conveying information and the latter will retain more of it. When used properly, new technology opens up a world of possibilities for educators and their students.

Overview of remote learning on its own. The phrases "distant learning" are now synonymous with "pandemic," "COVID-19," "shutdown," and many more. The integration of distant learning into classrooms was on the horizon, but it required a decisive push to take off. Even though you won't be able to see how beneficial it is until much later.

Move towards Blended Learning: The spread of COVID-19 has hastened the transition to online learning. A shift towards integrated learning was seen in educational institutions. It pushed for increased technological literacy among all educators. Massive prospects for a paradigm shift in pedagogy and curriculum creation arose as a result of new forms of learning delivery and evaluation. It also allows access to big groups of students all at once.

Rise in use of Learning Management Systems: There was a dramatic increase in the demand for learning management systems among schools. It was a huge boon for businesses that had been working on improving learning management systems for schools.

Enhance the use of soft copy of learning material: Since students were unable to access their physical copies of course materials during the lockdown, the majority of them relied on digital versions.

Improvement in collaborative work- Opportunities for innovative types of collaborative learning and teaching have recently emerged. Teachers and professors from all across the globe may work together to share knowledge and expertise.

Rise in online meetings- Teleconferencing, online meetings, webinars, and e-conferencing have all seen a dramatic increase in popularity since the epidemic.

Enhanced Digital Literacy: More individuals are literate in digital technologies since the pandemic condition pushed them to study and utilise them.

Improved the use of electronic media for sharing information: Students have easy access to course materials, and any questions they may have are answered via several social media platforms, including WhatsApp and Facebook, as well as traditional means of communication like email and SMS.

Worldwide exposure: Teachers and students alike are having the chance to network with people all across the globe. Students melted into a global village.

Better time Management: During pandemics, students may better manage their time using online education.

Demand for Open and Distance Learning (ODL): Most students preferred ODL mode during the epidemic because it promotes self-learning, gives access to a variety of materials, and allows for individualised instruction.

NEGATIVE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON EDUCATION:

These nations and pupils where poverty is a big problem felt the brunt of the pandemic's harmful effects. While it's true that pandemics have increased technology use in certain places, in others the complete suspension of schooling has occurred due to a lack of such tools. Although the concept of distance learning is simple in theory, it is really somewhat intricate. Computers (or other suitable devices), reliable internet access (speed internet is ideal), the right software packages, and so on are all necessary. Even though we live in a technologically advanced period, only 4.1 billion of the world's 7.5 billion inhabitants have access to the internet, and that doesn't even account for the number of individuals who own computers or have computer programmes installed.

Another problem with online education is that both teachers and students require training on how to utilise the many technological tools provided. Getting this done completely will take some time.

acclimated to the new methods, which causes even more sluggish instruction. If something is part of a larger problem, it could have an effect, but it is not the common problem. If things take too long, pupils may never have another chance to go back to school. Some students may not be able to continue their education into the next year because of the epidemic, according to reports. As a result, these students will either not be able to afford or physically attend classes. The lockdown or switching from offline to online sessions also poses some health risks. Students' well-being might be adversely affected by indoor activities, such as lessons or sessions. This claim may be defended by drawing parallels between traditional classroom instruction and online resources. It is possible to draw parallels between the two by comparing them fairly. The combination of the two assertions indicated before exacerbates the bad impact on health that comes from social isolation. Their capacity to scope the learning obstacles may be adversely affected by the modifications.

The federal and state governments issued notices and implemented technological solutions to help more

students in an effort to overcome this predicament and mitigate the negative effects of COVID-19 on the education sector. In an effort to combat this, the MHRD and other higher education authorities have invested much in reaching out to various demographics via various media platforms, tailoring their messaging to each. Some institutions in very remote areas have begun using radio as a medium for student instruction. With any luck, this strategy will allow all students to keep studying even while the world is in the midst of a pandemic.

Conclusion

Last but not least, a potential downside to travel is the anticipated explosion of teleconferencing options. A new kind of online conferencing platform may arise as a commercial model, and a lot of academic meetings, seminars, and conferences may shift online. Despite everything, we can predict one thing with absolute certainty: it will alter the face of higher education throughout the world, including in India. Now that higher education in India is undergoing reform, the country as a whole will undergo a dramatic change.

The post-COVID-19 era presents a chance to revamp the university system. This is a golden chance for educational institutions to reinvent themselves. Internationalising higher education should be a central emphasis of curriculum design, faculty engagement, skill development, and partnerships. Additionally, in order to be ready for any future pandemic scenarios, now is the perfect moment to enhance online education. Faculty members must take an active role in transforming the overall educational system. Students will have access to the world's top educators from any location thanks to a new age in education brought about by the unprecedented use of technology in the face of a catastrophe. Important characteristics anticipated for the future include the quality of the faculty, the familiarity of the faculty with digital teaching technology, and the quality of the IT infrastructure. Without a shadow of a doubt, the crisis has hastened the use of technology to impart knowledge and will eventually aid in fortifying the nation's digital learning infrastructure. "The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic will be felt for quite some time. Massive increases in the number of students taking lessons online from the comfort of their own homes will soon become the standard. This tendency was already increasing, but COVID-19 will give it a huge boost. Learning in a virtual classroom is just as excellent, if not better, than learning in a traditional classroom setting. An infinite number of courses may be brought to students' doorsteps via virtual classrooms, which is a very revolutionary capability. The COVID-19 pandemic has shook our nation's educational system to its very foundations. We might anticipate that COVID-19 will give rise to a new paradigm of education, similar to how the First Industrial Revolution shaped our current system.

References

1. Andersen, S C, and H S Nielsen (2019), "Learning from Performance Information", Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory
2. Alqurashi, E. (2018). Predicting student satisfaction and perceived learning with online learning environments. Journal of Distance Education, 40(1), 133-148.
- 3 WHO. WHO Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Dashboard. Retrieved on June 3, 2020. From <https://covid19.who.int/>
4. Wikipedia. Covid-19 Pandemic in India. Retrieved on May 20, 2020 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COVID-19_pandemic_in_India
- 5 Wikipedia, Education in India Retrieved on May 24, 2020. From https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education_in_India
- 6 . bUNESCO. COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response. Retrieved on June 3, 2020 from <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
7. DNS Kumar (29 April 2020). Impact of COVID-19 on Higher Education. Retrieved on May 25, 2020 from <https://www.highereducationdigest.com/impact-of-covid-19-on-highereducation/>
8. Pravat Ku Jena. Challenges and Opportunities created by Covid-19 for ODL: A case study of IGNOU. International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Filed. 2020a; 6(5):217-222.
- 9 . Pravat Ku Jena. Impact of Pandemic COVID-19 on Education in India. Purakala. 2020b; 31(46):142-149.